

Tuning the mechanical and thermo-mechanical responses of bio nanocomposite films of plasticized polylactic acid with halloysite nanotubes

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Preparation of bio-nanocomposite films of PLA

Bio-nanocomposite films

Tensile and thermo-mechanical properties of nanocomposite films

SEM of tensile fractured composite films

FINDINGS

- Addition of PEG and/or HNT reduces the transparency of the films.
- PEG acts as a plasticizer and improves the elongation of PLA films.
- HNT acts as reinforcement and improves the thermal stability of the composite films and shows significant improvement in the strength as compare to plasticized PLA (PLA/PEG).
- Composite films of PLA with PEG and HNT showed highest storage modulus in rubbery stage.